

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME COMPLEXES

Compound No.	Infrared Spectra (cm ⁻¹)					Electronic spectra ν_{\max} in kK (ϵ)
	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$	
1	1575	720	1000	340	280	22.0(1), 22.4(2), 24.6(2)
4	1570	720	1000	330	290	19.0(38), 20.3
6	1575	725	995	335	290	19.2(35), 20.2
7	1570	720	995	325	295	9.5(7), 13.8(8), 24.6(12)
10	1575	720	1000	330	290	15.0(58)
12	1570	725	1000	335	295	13.8(45)
14	1575	720	990	340	290	14.3(48)
17	1570	725	1000	335	295	—
19	1575	720	1000	330	290	—

cm⁻¹ whereas $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ is found around 700 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Thus, the ligand behaves as bidentate in all the complexes where bonding occurs through the azomethine nitrogen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms. This has been confirmed by the observation⁸ of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ around 325-340 and 280-295 cm⁻¹, respectively.

In the thiocyanato complexes, $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ is found around 2090 cm⁻¹ indicating⁴ the presence of terminal N-bonded thiocyanato group. Nitrate complexes show the ν_2 and ν_1 bands around 1420 and 1280 cm⁻¹ region and their difference of the order of 140 cm⁻¹ indicates^{5,6} monodentate nitrate group coordination. In case of zinc and cadmium perchlorate complexes one broad band is found around 1100 cm⁻¹ indicating^{7,8} ionic perchlorate group in conformity with their molar conductance data. Other perchlorate complexes exhibit three distinct bands in the 1000-1160 cm⁻¹ region confirming the covalent nature of perchlorate group in these compounds.

Visible electronic spectra of manganese complexes show three bands around 20.0, 22.4 and 24.6 kK attributable to ${}^6\text{A}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1$ (G), $\rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_2$ (G) and $\rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_1$ (G) transitions, respectively. The band positions and intensity values suggest⁹ a tetrahedral stereochemistry for these complexes. Cobalt complexes show the main band around 19.0 kK with a shoulder on the high frequency side attributable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition, the shoulder being the consequence of splitting due to spin-orbit coupling. Thus the band positions, intensity and magnetic moment value support octahedral stereochemistry for the compounds. Nickel chloride and thiocyanato complexes exhibit three absorption bands around 9.5, 13.8 and 24.6 kK regions characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry in conformity with their magnetic moment values. Nickel nitrate and perchlorate complexes show one broad band at ~15.0 kK ($\epsilon=58$) supporting¹⁰ a square planar configuration of the complexes in agreement with their diamagnetic nature. In case of copper complexes one broad absorption band is observed around 13.8-14.5 kK region suggesting¹¹ a distorted octahedral configuration for these compounds. On the basis of analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data zinc and cadmium complexes appear

to have tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

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Synthesis and Spectral Studies on Complexes of *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of 3-Acetyl-4-Hydroxy Coumarin Glyoxal with Pt⁴⁺, Ir³⁺ and UO₂²⁺ Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 12 June 1981, revised 5 November 1982, accepted 28 April 1983

COUMARIN derivatives have found extensive application in medicine and biology and they are also known for their complex forming tendencies. We describe here the preparation and characterisation of complexes of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy coumarin glyoxal with some third

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)				
		C	H	N	OI	Metal
[Pt(C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)] ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Buff	49.65 (49.62)	3.98 (3.94)	6.11 (6.09)	—	21.27 (21.20)
[Ir(C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Yellow	49.06 (48.84)	4.00 (3.66)	5.91 (5.99)	3.81 (3.79)	20.49 (20.57)
[UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂)]NO ₃	Yellowish grey	33.32 (33.29)	2.25 (2.50)	6.25 (6.13)	—	34.61 (34.72)

row transition metal ions e.g. Ir³⁺, Pt⁴⁺ and UO₂²⁺ metal ions. The values of ligand field splitting energy (10 Dq), Racah interelectronic repulsion parameters (B and C), nephelauxetic ratio (β), $\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1}$, and L.F.S.E. are calculated. The results are briefly discussed in an attempt to determine the stereochemistry around the cation and the nature of bonding. K(M-O) and K(M-N) stretching force constants have also been worked out.

Experimental

Preparation of the compound: The compound is prepared by condensing 3-acetyl-4-OH-coumarin glyoxal hydrate with *p*-dimethyl amino aniline¹. The glyoxal is prepared by the usual method of the oxidation of 3-acetyl-4-OH-coumarin with selenium dioxide² in alcohol. The condensation was carried out according to the literature methods³. Both were taken in equimolar amounts (0.01) in ethanol (10 ml) and refluxed on water bath for 30 min to yield buff coloured crystals on crystallisation with ethanol. Elemental analyses indicated a molecular formula C₁₀H₁₀O₄N₂. (Found: C, 67.92; H, 4.72; N, 8.37. Calcd.: C, 67.85; H, 4.76; N, 8.33%).

Preparation and isolation of the complexes: The complexes were prepared by mixing the metal salts, uranyl nitrate UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (B.D.H. AnalaR), iridium chloride IrCl₃·H₂O (Fluka) and chloroplatinic acid H₂PtCl₆·4H₂O (B.D.H.), and the ligand in the required ratio in ethanol. After refluxing the mixture for ~ 1 hr on water bath and removal of the alcohol by distillation, the coloured precipitate started appearing, which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in an air oven at 80°. Stoichiometry of the isolated complexes was established by chemical analyses and ir techniques. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements: IR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, model 521 using KBr pellets. Magnetic moments were determined by Guoy method at room temperature. The electronic spectra of the isolated complexes were run on Hilger Uvispek and Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometers, at room temperature using pure solvent in each case as reference.

TABLE 2—IR DATA OF THE LIGAND AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH Pt⁴⁺, Ir³⁺ AND UO₂²⁺ (cm⁻¹)

Ligand	Pt ⁴⁺ Com- plex	Ir ³⁺ Com- plex	UO ₂ ²⁺ Com- plex	Assignments of bands
—	3360	3500	3380	δ (H ₂ O)
—	1610	1630	1620	ν (OH)
3400	—	—	—	(OH) Phenolic
1675	1600	1604	1610	>C=O
1650	1500	1570	1590	-CH=N
1283	1283	1280	1280	ν (C-O) + δ (C-H) + ν (N-O)
—	490	500	510	ν (M-O)
—	400	440	470	ν (M-N)
			940	ν_2 UO ₂ ²⁺ Asym. Stretch
			845	ν_1 UO ₂ ²⁺ Sym. Stretch

Results and Discussion

The complexes are coloured fine powders. They are insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents. Analytical data of the prepared complexes suggest 1:2 (M:L) stoichiometry in Pt(IV) and Ir(III) complexes and 1:1 in UO₂(VI) complex.

The magnetic measurements reveal that Pt and Ir complexes are diamagnetic in nature. The magnetic moment value for UO₂²⁺ complex was found to be 0.53 B.M. which is much below the expected value for one unpaired electron and may be due to temperature independent paramagnetism⁴.

The ir spectral data of the ligand and its complexes have been interpreted on the lines of previously reported data⁵⁻⁶. The medium broad band appearing at 3400 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand has been assigned to phenolic OH. On complexation, this frequency completely disappears suggesting the formation of a bond between the metal and phenolic oxygen by the loss of proton from the phenolic group. Also, the bands due to C=O and -CH=N get lowered on complexation, indicating the formation⁷⁻⁸ of a C=O...M covalent bond and -CH=N...M coordinate bond. The medium intensity band in the ligand at 1283 cm⁻¹ shows an unusual increase in intensity and becomes broad. This may be considered to be a mixture of ν (C-O) + δ (C-H) + ν (N-O) vibrations. The M-N stretching frequency⁷ is of special interest since it provides direct information regarding the coordinate bond. Because of relatively heavy mass of metal and low bond order of the coordinate bond, the M-N stretching vibrations may appear in the

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND RELEVANT LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Complex	Observed bands cm ⁻¹	Assignments	10 Dq cm ⁻¹	Racah's parameters cm ⁻¹		$\frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}$	Nephelauxetic ratio β	L. F. S. E. k.cal/mole
				B	C			
[Pt(O ₂ H _{1.5} O ₄ N ₂) ₂].3H ₂ O	15600	¹ A _{1g} → ³ T _{1g}	22500	300	2300	1.153	0.416	52.45
	18000	→ ³ T _{2g}						
	20200	→ ¹ T _{1g}						
	38030	¹ T _{1u}						
	42230	¹ T _{1u}						
[Ir(O ₂ H _{1.5} O ₄ N ₂) ₂].Cl.2H ₂ O	20320	¹ A _{1g} → ³ T _{1g}	30175	329	3285	1.19	0.49	51.72
	26890	→ ¹ T _{1g}						
	32160	→ ¹ T _{2g}						

lower frequency region. Therefore, the bands appearing between 400-470 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to (M-N) linkages. The bands observed at 490 cm⁻¹ in the Ir complex, at 500 cm⁻¹ in the Pt complex and at 510 cm⁻¹ in the UO₂²⁺ complex have been assigned to ν (M-O) vibration mode. K(M-O) and K(M-N) stretching force constants are presented in Table 4. It is interesting to note that K(M-O) and K(M-N) stretching force constants in the Ir complex are greater than that of Pt complex.

TABLE 4—K(M-O) AND K(M-N) STRETCHING FORCE CONSTANTS (mdyne/Å)

Complex	K(M-O)	K(M-N)
[Pt(O ₂ H _{1.5} O ₄ N ₂) ₂].3H ₂ O	2.091	1.231
[Ir(O ₂ H _{1.5} O ₄ N ₂) ₂].Cl.2H ₂ O	2.174	1.480
[UO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂) ₂].H ₂ O].NO ₂	2.296	1.721

The absorption bands at 3360-3500 cm⁻¹ and 1610-1640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes clearly confirm the presence of water of crystallisation in the complexes.

The uranyl ion is reported⁹ to exhibit three characteristic absorption bands, symmetric stretching (ν_1), symmetric bending (ν_2) and antisymmetric (ν_3). According to the selection rules, for the linear structure (D_{∞h}) of UO₂²⁺ ion, only ν_1 should appear in Raman spectrum and ν_2 and ν_3 in the infrared spectrum. However, these selection rules are not strictly valid for the ions under the influence of crystalline fields. It has been observed¹⁰⁻¹¹ that ν_1 appears with weak intensity and ν_3 with strong intensity in the infrared spectra. Therefore, the weak band at 845 cm⁻¹ and the very strong band at 940 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν_1 and ν_3 vibrations of uranyl group in UO₂²⁺ complex. The nitrate ion shows absorption bands at ~ 1390 cm⁻¹ which on coordination gets split into two strong bands approximately at 1500 and 1280 cm⁻¹. The additional band observed in uranyl complex at 1270 cm⁻¹ may not be other than that of the nitrate ion in the complex. The appearance of ν_3 fundamental with strong intensity and ν_1 fundamental with very weak intensity indicates that even in complex the UO₂²⁺ ion maintains its linearity.

The electronic spectral data and relevant ligand field parameters are recorded in Table 3. The Pt(IV) complex shows three transitions at 15600(γ_1), 18000(γ_2) and 20200 cm⁻¹, which are assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g}, respectively¹². In addition to three d-d transitions, two charge transfer bands at 38030 and 42230 cm⁻¹ have also been observed, which have been assigned to ligand-metal charge transfer bands. In Ir(III) complex three bands at 20320, 26890 (γ_1) and 32160 (γ_2) cm⁻¹ are observed, which are assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions, respectively. These absorption bands suggest an octahedral geometry for these complexes. The ratio of γ_2/γ_1 has been found to be 1.15 for Pt complex and 1.19 for Ir complex, which further support octahedral geometry of the complexes. The value of 10 Dq and Racah's parameters B and C have been calculated using equations¹³⁻¹⁴: $E(^3T_{1g}) = 10 Dq - 3C$, $E(^3T_{2g}) = 10 Dq + 8B - 3C$, $E(^3T_{1g}) = 10 Dq - C$ and $E(^1T_{2g}) = 10 Dq + 16B - C$. The values of 10 Dq suggest strong interaction between metal ion and organic molecule and β values indicate that complexes are covalent in nature. The electronic spectra of UO₂(VI) complex also show three bands at 33000, 34340 and 41620 cm⁻¹, which have been assigned to charge transfer from ligand to metal ion and transitions within the ligand. Similar trend was observed earlier in the uranyl β -diketone complexes¹⁵⁻¹⁶.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to Dr. A. N. Pandey, Department of Physics, Meerut College, Meerut for his interest in this work. One of the authors (V.K.R.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship.

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Dimeric Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) Complexes of Tridentate ONN Donor Ligands

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Manuscript received 31 October 1981, revised 3 August 1982,

accepted 28 April 1983

THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L), 2,5-dihydroxypropionophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L') and 2,5-dihydroxybenzophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L'').

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxyacetophenone/propionophenone/benzophenone¹ were refluxed with *p*-aminoazobenzene on a water-bath. The reaction mixture in each case was concentrated and cooled in a freezing bath. Shinning yellow Schiff bases that separated out by adding small pieces of ice to the reaction mixture were filtered and crystallised from alcohol. They are insoluble in water and soluble in common organic solvents. The melting points are 169, 182 and 155°, respectively.

Ethanolic solutions of the Schiff base and the metal salt ($CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ or $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) were mixed in 1:1 molar ratio and refluxed on a water-bath for 1.5 hr. The reaction mixture concentrated and the pH raised to 8 by adding 1:1 ammonia in alcohol, to give yellowish-green copper, bluish-green nickel and brownish-red cobalt complexes that were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in a desiccator.

Nitrogen, chloride and metal ions were estimated by the standard methods². Molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF and the molecular weight was determined cryoscopically³. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy balance. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, conductance, magnetic and spectral data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The elemental analyses indicate 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. The low molar conductance values of the complexes are ascribed to their non-electrolytic nature. The observed molecular weight values of the complexes suggest their dimeric character.

The assignments of ir bands of the ligands and the complexes are based on literature^{4,5}. In the ligands, the band observed at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to νOH frequency and the additional band broad and weak at $\sim 2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to νOH involved in intramolecular H-bonding with basic azomethine nitrogen. In the complexes the νOH band is retained whereas the low frequency band disappears suggesting that the phenolic proton involved in O-H...N bonding is lost on complex formation. This is further confirmed by the appearance of a new $\nu(M-O)$ band at $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. However, the $\nu(C-H)$ band observed at $\sim 3070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands is not affected on complex formation. The strong band due to $\nu(C=N)$ observed at $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands is found to shift by 15-20 cm^{-1} to lower frequency region on complex formation. This suggests that the azomethine nitrogen is bonded to the metal ion. The $\nu(M-N)$ band is observed in the complexes at $\sim 385\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is cumbersome to assign the $\nu(N=N)$ mode to a specific band due to extensive coupling amongst $\nu(C=C)$, $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N=N)$ modes. However, the band observed at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is tentatively assigned to coupled $\nu(C=C)$ and $\nu(N=N)$ modes. This band shifts by 45-65 cm^{-1} to lower frequency region in the complexes suggesting that the nitrogen of N=N group is bonded to metal ion. The occurrence of $\nu(M-Cl)$ band at $\sim 340\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes indicate that the chlorine atom occupies the fourth coordination position of the metal(II) ions.

The μ_{eff} values of the complexes (Table 1) are slightly less than the values suggested for a tetrahedral geometry⁶. The ligand geometry (Fig. 1) indicates that a monomeric structure involves much steric hindrance. A dimeric formulation requires appreciable reduction in the magnetic moment values of a complex. In the case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes the magnetic moment values are close to their spin-only values. We suggest a

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